

Den Haag Persistent Object Identifier – Linked Open Data Manifesto

Background

The following text was proposed by break out group 3 at the Knowledge Exchange Persistent Object Identifier workshop which was held at the DANS office in Den Haag on June 14 and 15, 2011¹. This manifesto is intended as the basis for a co-ordinated approach to identifier issues across the persistent identifier (PID) and linked open data (LOD) communities. The intention was to try and state what the PID and the LOD approaches can each learn from the other, and what elements of each other's infrastructure they could adopt.

After the workshop the manifesto text was made available as an editable Google Doc for any of the attendees to edit the text or add comments. The resulting text is shown below. None of the principles were changed as a result of this process, but the comments that were made have been merged, de-identified, and shown after each principle.

Principles

1. Make sure PIDs can be referred to as HTTP URI's, including support for content negotiation.

Commentary:

- <http://inkdroid.org/journal/2011/04/25/does-as-linked-data/>

2. Use appropriate LOD vocabularies to populate schema elements

Commentary:

- Need to define what constitutes appropriate, and this may well depend on the community being served
- schema elements here refers to the metadata schema for the particular persistent identifier mechanism

¹ For more information, including the presentations, please see: <http://www.knowledge-exchange.info/Default.aspx?ID=440>

3. Identify the minimum common set of schema elements across different kinds of identifiers in the scholarly communication space.

Commentary:

- DataCite has already defined a minimum set
- Who is going to do this work, and for which kinds of identifiers? There are lots of extant schemes
- Is the purpose to establish minimum metadata for PIDs? If so, why?

4. Use same-as relations to help PID interoperability across PID systems/schemas

Commentary:

- Potential difficulties here; if this means owl:sameAs, then we have to be really sure they are the same in all discernable respects, or unexpected inferences may be available. The phrasing here suggests some less strict relation, which would be OK, but begs *what* same-as relation(s) might be appropriate
- Concerns whether this approach could scale sufficiently

5. Use Persistent IDs for Subjects and Objects

Commentary:

- Why not also use Persistent IDs for Predicates also?

6. Work with the LOD community on simple policies/procedures to improve persistence of HTTP URIs

Commentary:

- Offer the LOD community persistent resolution services for the PIDs, and they will treat PIDs as URI citizens of LOD

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